

Funder aims to boost open science practices

[This is a preprint of a letter to the Editor accepted for publication in the Correspondence section of Nature. It was written on invitation by the Editor at the occasion of the announcement (on the 27th of October, 2021) by the Dutch Research Council of the results of the first round of the NWO Open Science Fund].

Researchers are increasingly expected to pursue open science in the form of open-access publication and data sharing. To help promote this movement, the Dutch Research Council (NWO) has set up an Open Science Fund for research projects specifically designed to stimulate open-science practices (<https://www.openaccess.nl/en/events/dutch-research-council-launches-open-science-fund>).

The response from the Dutch research community has been overwhelming. We received 167 eligible proposals, of which 26 were funded in the first round (<https://www.nwo.nl/en/researchprogrammes/open-science/open-science-fund/open-science-fund-2021-awarded-grants>). The projects include the development of innovative publication practices and of open-source tools and software that facilitate open science; devising and setting standards for data sharing; and promoting a cultural shift towards open science.

For open science to become the norm (see: Curry, Stephen; de Rijcke, Sarah; Hatch, Anna; Pillay, Dorsamy (Gansen); van der Weijden, Inge; Wilsdon, James (2020): The changing role of funders in responsible research assessment: progress, obstacles and the way ahead. Research on Research Institute. Report. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13227914.v1>), we suggest that funders need to recognize and encourage researchers' participation in open science. The European Commission recently announced a move in this direction: open-science will be assessed as part of the scientific methodology under the excellence criterion of Horizon Europe's research-funding programme (see https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-13-general-annexes_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf).

November 9, 2021

Hans de Jonge ([ORCID](#)), Maria Cruz ([ORCID](#)), Stephanie Holst ([ORCID](#))
Dutch Research Council (NWO)
The Hague, the Netherlands.
h.dejonge@nwo.nl